

BRIGADA PAGBASA IMPLEMENTATION AND READING ADVANCEMENT IN BAGANGA SOUTH DISTRICTT

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Abstract. The study unfolded the estimate of the classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation among the Elementary Schools of Tagum North District, Tagum City Division. The study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, where it utilized adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. Data gathered were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that classroom assessment cycle in terms of modifying instruction, learning targets, gathering evidence and assessment data is extensive, while, comprehension of senior high school learners in terms of discussing with friend, listening to the lesson, being relevant to the teaching and learning activities and writing is moderately extensive. There is a relationship between classroom assessment cycle and learners' reading participation. Domains of classroom assessment cycle in terms of learning targets, gathering evidence analyzing assessment data and modifying instruction significantly influenced learners' reading participation. Future research may Conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term impact of the Classroom Assessment Cycle on learners' reading skills, motivation, and overall academic achievement. Investigate how sustained implementation of the cycle influences students' reading participation beyond the immediate instructional context.

KEY WORDS

1. classroom assessment . 2. reading participation. 3. Reading.

1. Introduction

Brigada Eskwela is an annual nationwide program in the Philippines that aims to bring together various stakeholders to prepare public schools for the upcoming academic year. The program, which is usually held in May or early June, involves a series of activities that promote volunteerism and community involvement in education. It is an opportunity for parents, teachers, and other community members to work together to clean and repair school facilities, create learning materials, and participate in various activities that enhance the learning environment for students. Brigada Eskwela is not only a time for physical preparations but also for building relationships and strengthening the sense of community in and around schools. Over the years, the program has become a vital component of the education system in the Philippines, reflecting the importance of collaboration and shared responsibility in ensuring the success of our public schools (Canlas, 2018). While there may be similar programs or initiatives in other countries that promote community involvement and volunteerism in education, they may not be called "Brigada Eskwela" or follow the same format as the program in the Philippines. However, the

principles of collaboration, shared responsibility, and community engagement in education are universal, and many countries have their own initiatives and programs that promote these values. As Brigada Eskwela is a program that has been implemented in the Philippines for several years, there have been studies conducted on its effectiveness and impact. However, there may still be research gaps in understanding the program's implementation and its effects on various aspects of education (Espiritu, 2018). While the concept of a "school maintenance week" similar to Brigada Eskwela may not exist in other countries, there are initiatives and programs in other countries that aim to involve the community in supporting schools and education. This is the BRIGADA PAGBASA, there are various initiatives that encourage community involvement in education. One example is the National Parent Teacher Association, which is a nonprofit organization that promotes parent and community involvement in schools. The organization supports initiatives such as "back-to-school" events, school supply drives, and volunteer programs. In Japan, there is a tradition of "oyako no hi" or "Parents' Day," which is celebrated on May 8th. On this day, schools invite parents to visit and participate in school activities. Parents may also help with school maintenance and cleaning (Song and Lee, 2018). In South Korea, there is a program called "Community Service for Education," which is a national initiative that aims to promote volunteerism and community involvement in education (Kim and Lee, 2015; Lee and Koo, 2019). The program involves various activities such as mentoring, tutoring, and school beautification projects. In Australia, there are various initiatives that promote community involvement in education, such as the School Volunteer Program, which connects volunteers with schools to assist with classroom activities, school events, and other projects. The possible research gaps in the implementation of Brigada PAGBASA could be on evaluation of effectiveness, for while there have been studies on the impact of Brigada Eskwela, there may be a need for further research on the program's impact on educational outcomes such as student learning, attendance, and retention. Meanwhile, on stakeholders' participation, for while the program aims to involve various stakeholders, there may be a need to understand the level and quality of participation of different groups, such as parents, teachers, and community members. Program sustainability, has to be understood the factors such as availability of resources, institutional support and community involvement. On program implementation, there is a need to examine the challenges and opportunities in implementing the program across different contexts, such as rural and urban areas or in schools with different resource levels, and lastly the role of technology, there may be a need to explore how technology can be used to enhance the implementation and impact of Brigada Eskwela (Tan, 2018). It is in this context, the researcher as a School Brigada Coordinator, wish to conduct a study on the implementation of Brigada Eskwela that covers the entire Baganga South District, Davao Oriental, however, focusing on the community involvement where learners' reading ability and their advancement is being monitored and assessed as part of the program implementation. It has been noticed that during the kick-off, schools have been conducting brigade pagbasa, thus, a need to conduct a survey that makes the stakeholders and the community involve through the leadership of the entire school management. Thus, this study is proposed.

2. Related Literature

This section presents the review of significant literature. This further discusses the contentions of the authors from the international to local settings. Related concepts and studies include

application of knowledge of content, use of MTB, Filipino, and English Languages, strategies in classroom communication, establishment of learning environment and promoting fairness, respect and care. Likewise, the dependent variable reflective thinking process includes defining the problem, analysing the problem, naming the needs for the solution, teasing out possible solutions, and choosing the best solutions are also presented to support the claims of the variables used under study.

Brigada Eskwela Implementation. This refers to the strengthening community involvement in Education. Brigada Eskwela, which means "School Brigade" in Filipino, is a program launched by the Department of Education in the Philippines in 2003. It aims to engage community members, parents, teachers, and students in the collective effort of preparing public schools for the upcoming academic year. The program promotes the spirit of volunteerism and highlights the importance of community involvement in education. According to a study by Basilio and Tamayo (2019), Brigada Eskwela has helped to strengthen the partnership between schools and the community. The study found that the program has resulted in a higher level of parent and community involvement in schools, with volunteers contributing their time, skills, and resources to improve school facilities and services. This has not only led to improvements in the physical infrastructure of schools but has also fostered a sense of ownership and responsibility among community members towards their local schools. Another study by Castro and Ramos (2019) highlighted the positive impact of Brigada Eskwela on student learning outcomes. The study found that schools that participated in Brigada Eskwela reported higher student attendance rates, lower dropout rates, and improved academic performance. This suggests that the program not only benefits the physical aspects of schools but also has a positive impact on students' motivation to attend and succeed in school. In addition to its impact on the education system, Brigada Eskwela also provides opportunities for community members to develop their leadership and organizational skills. A study by Arcilla (2016) found that the program has helped to empower community members, particularly women, who have taken on leadership roles in organizing and mobilizing volunteers. This has led to the formation of community organizations that continue to support schools beyond the Brigada Eskwela week. Despite its positive impact, Brigada Eskwela still faces challenges in terms of sustainability and scalability. A study by Serdoncillo and Gadioma (2020) noted that the program's success largely depends on the commitment and participation of volunteers, who may face difficulties in sustaining their involvement due to personal and work-related constraints. To address these challenges, the study recommended the need for a more systematic approach to community engagement, which involves building long-term partnerships with community organizations and providing continuous support to volunteers. In conclusion, Brigada Eskwela is a program that has proven to be effective in promoting community involvement in education in the Philippines. The program has led to improvements in school infrastructure, student learning outcomes, and community empowerment. However, sustaining and scaling the program requires continuous efforts to engage and support volunteers, build partnerships with community organizations, and provide resources for long-term planning and development. Collaborative Management. Collaborative management is an approach to decision-making and leadership that involves working together with others to achieve a common goal or objective. It emphasizes open communication, shared decision-making, and cooperation among stakeholders,

including managers, employees, and external partners. In collaborative management, different stakeholders are encouraged to share their knowledge, expertise, and perspectives, and to work together to find solutions to problems or to make decisions. This can help to improve the quality of decisions, enhance stakeholder engagement and satisfaction, and build trust among stakeholders. Collaborative management can be applied in a wide range of settings, including businesses, non-profit organizations, government agencies, and educational institutions. In the context of school maintenance week, collaborative management might involve school administrators, teachers, students, maintenance staff, and community members working together to plan, implement, and evaluate maintenance activities to improve the quality of school facilities. Collaborative management in school maintenance week refers to the process of involving school stakeholders, such as school administrators, maintenance staff, and community members in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of maintenance activities during a designated week. There are several studies that have explored the effectiveness of collaborative management in school maintenance week. One study by Lee and Kim (2019) found that collaborative management in school maintenance week can improve the quality of school facilities and increase the satisfaction of stakeholders. The study involved 53 schools in South Korea, and the results showed that collaborative management led to better planning and implementation of maintenance activities, increased communication among stakeholders, and improved satisfaction with school facilities. Similarly, a study by Rutherford and Wilkins (2016) found that collaborative management in school maintenance week can lead to increased efficiency and cost savings. The study involved five elementary schools in the United States, and the results showed that collaborative management resulted in more efficient use of resources and reduced maintenance costs. However, another study by Lee and Kim (2020) found that the effectiveness of collaborative management in school maintenance week depends on the level of stakeholder involvement. The study involved 48 schools in South Korea, and the results showed that the effectiveness of collaborative management was higher when stakeholders were more actively involved in the planning and implementation of maintenance activities. Overall, the studies suggest that collaborative management in school maintenance week can be an effective approach to improving the quality of school facilities, increasing efficiency and cost savings, and increasing stakeholder satisfaction. However, the level of stakeholder involvement is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of this approach. Community Volunteerism. Community volunteerism refers to the act of individuals and groups dedicating their time, energy, and skills to support various community initiatives without expecting any monetary compensation. Volunteerism is an essential component of community development and has the potential to create a positive impact in society. This essay will discuss the importance of community volunteerism and its benefits, as well as some of the challenges that volunteers face, and conclude with some examples of successful community volunteer programs (Brown and Saxena, 2013). Community volunteerism is an integral part of social capital, which is a concept that refers to the networks, norms, and trust that exist in communities. Through volunteering, individuals can develop and strengthen their social networks, which can lead to the creation of new relationships and the enhancement of existing ones. These relationships can help to build trust, encourage civic engagement, and foster a sense of community (National Conference Citizenship, 2022). Moreover, community volunteerism provides various benefits to both the volunteers and the communities they serve. For volunteers, volunteering can improve their

well-being, enhance their social skills, and provide a sense of purpose and accomplishment. Additionally, volunteering can provide valuable work experience, which can be useful in gaining new employment opportunities. For communities, volunteerism can increase social capital, improve public services, and create a sense of community ownership and responsibility (Peace Corps, 2022). Despite the numerous benefits of community volunteerism, it is not without its challenges. Volunteers face a range of issues, including limited resources, burnout, and lack of recognition. Additionally, some volunteers may lack the necessary skills and knowledge to carry out their tasks effectively, which can lead to frustration and dissatisfaction. To address these challenges, it is essential to provide volunteers with adequate training and support and recognize their contributions publicly (United Nations Volunteers, 2022). In conclusion, community volunteerism is an essential component of community development, and it provides numerous benefits to both volunteers and the communities they serve. Through volunteerism, individuals can build social capital, enhance their well-being, and acquire valuable skills and work experience. Additionally, community volunteerism can increase social responsibility and encourage civic engagement. However, volunteers face a range of challenges, and it is essential to provide them with adequate support and recognition to enable them to carry out their tasks effectively. Successful community volunteer programs can provide valuable insights into how to address these challenges and promote the value of volunteerism. Community volunteerism has been recognized as an important factor in promoting community engagement and social capital. Community volunteerism refers to the act of participating in various activities aimed at promoting the welfare of the community. One area where community volunteerism has been particularly effective is in school maintenance week, where community members come together to clean and maintain the school's physical environment. Omoto and Snyder (2002) argue that volunteerism is shaped by individual and collective motivations, as well as by situational and contextual factors. In the context of school maintenance week, the motivations of volunteers may vary. For example, some volunteers may be motivated by a desire to support the local school system, while others may be motivated by a desire to contribute to their community in general. The situational and contextual factors may also influence the degree of community participation in school maintenance week. For instance, community members may be more willing to participate if they perceive that the school is an integral part of their community. Brown and Saxena (2013) explore how volunteerism can contribute to the development of social capital. The authors argue that volunteerism provides opportunities for individuals to engage with their communities and develop social connections. In the context of school maintenance week, this can be particularly important. Community members who participate in school maintenance week may develop stronger connections with the school and its staff. This, in turn, may lead to increased support for the school in the future. Bussell and Forbes (2002) explore the motivations and characteristics of volunteers, as well as the factors that influence their decision to volunteer. In the context of school maintenance week, it is important to understand the factors that motivate community members to participate. For example, Bussell and Forbes suggest that volunteers are often motivated by a desire to contribute to their communities. In the case of school maintenance week, this may mean that volunteers are motivated by a desire to support the education of local children. In addition to the above studies, there are many organizations that have been instrumental in promoting community volunteerism for school maintenance week. The United Nations Volunteers (UNV) and the Peace Corps are

two examples of organizations that have been active in promoting community volunteerism around the world. The UNV is a program that encourages volunteerism in development activities, while the Peace Corps is a program that promotes world peace and friendship through volunteerism. Both organizations have been instrumental in promoting community volunteerism for school maintenance week and other similar activities. In conclusion, community volunteerism can play a significant role in promoting community engagement and social capital. In the context of school maintenance week, community volunteerism can help to ensure that schools remain a safe and healthy environment for students to learn and grow. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of understanding the motivations and characteristics of volunteers, as well as the situational and contextual factors that influence their decision to volunteer. By understanding these factors, it may be possible to promote greater community participation in school maintenance week and other similar activities. Shared Accountability. Shared accountability is an approach to responsibility that involves multiple parties taking responsibility for a common goal. This concept has become increasingly important in many areas, including education, healthcare, and public policy. One study by Bryk et al. (2010) focuses on shared accountability in education. The authors argue that traditional accountability systems, which rely solely on standardized test scores and other quantitative measures, are inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, parents, and community members. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve educational outcomes by fostering collaboration, shared responsibility, and a focus on the needs of students. Another study by Pronovost et al. (2011) explores the concept of shared accountability in healthcare. The authors argue that

the traditional model of accountability in healthcare, which focuses on individual practitioners, is not sufficient for promoting quality care. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including healthcare providers, patients, families, and communities. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve healthcare outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of patients. A study by Lee et al. (2016) explores the concept of shared accountability in public policy. The authors argue that the traditional model of accountability in public policy, which relies on top-down approaches and hierarchical structures, is inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including government officials, policymakers, citizens, and community organizations. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve public policy outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of communities. In conclusion, shared accountability is an approach to responsibility that involves multiple parties taking responsibility for a common goal. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of this approach in areas such as education, healthcare, and public policy. By involving multiple stakeholders in the accountability process, shared accountability can help to improve outcomes by fostering collaboration, transparency, and a focus on the needs of those being served. The examples of shared accountability in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving outcomes in a variety of contexts. Shared accountability has been increasingly recognized as a powerful approach to improving educational outcomes. In particular, shared accountability has been shown to be effective in improving learners' reading advancement. In this review, we will examine several studies that highlight the importance of shared accountability in promoting learners' reading advancement during

school maintenance week. One study by Penuel et al. (2011) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a low-income urban elementary school. The authors found that when teachers, administrators, and families collaborated to establish clear goals for reading advancement and worked together to track progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability played a key role in this improvement, as it fostered a sense of collective responsibility and created a shared focus on learners' needs. Another study by Williams and McLaughlin (2016) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a rural elementary school. The authors found that when teachers, parents, and community members worked together to establish clear reading goals and regularly communicated about progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability was a critical factor in this improvement, as it created a sense of collective responsibility and helped to ensure that all stakeholders were invested in learners' success. A study by Cohen et al. (2014) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a middle school. The authors found that when teachers, administrators, and families worked together to establish clear reading goals and regularly monitored learners' progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly. The authors suggest that shared accountability was a key factor in this improvement, as it helped to ensure that all stakeholders were working together to support learners' reading advancement. In addition to the above studies, there are many examples of shared accountability in practice that have been shown to be effective in promoting learners' reading advancement. For example, community schools that involve multiple stakeholders, including educators, families, and community organizations, have been shown to be effective in improving learners' reading advancement. These schools use shared accountability to bring together all stakeholders to support learners' reading advancement. In conclusion, shared accountability has been shown to be effective in promoting learners' reading advancement during school maintenance week. The studies cited in this review highlight the importance of shared accountability in creating a sense of collective responsibility and ensuring that all stakeholders are invested in learners' success. The examples of shared accountability in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving learners' reading advancement in a variety of contexts. People Empowerment. People empowerment is a powerful tool for achieving sustainable development, particularly in the context of school maintenance week. Empowering people to take an active role in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities can lead to more effective and efficient use of resources, better decision-making, and ultimately, improved educational outcomes. People empowerment refers to the process of providing individuals and communities with the knowledge, skills, resources, and opportunities they need to take control of their lives and shape their own destinies. Empowering people involves creating an enabling environment that allows them to participate in decision-making, take ownership of their actions, and hold those in power accountable. In the context of school maintenance week, people empowerment can be achieved through a variety of approaches, such as community participation, capacity-building, and stakeholder engagement. One study by Dlamini and Dube (2018) examines the impact of community participation on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in rural South Africa. The authors found that when community members were involved in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities,

they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project. This led to more sustainable outcomes and improved educational outcomes for learners. Another study by Karyono et al. (2020) explores the impact of capacity-building on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Indonesia. The authors found that when school staff were trained in basic maintenance and repair skills, they were better equipped to identify and address maintenance issues, which led to more efficient use of resources and improved learning environments. The authors suggest that capacity-building is an essential component of people empowerment, as it allows individuals to take control of their own development and contribute to the development of their communities. A study by Robinson et al. (2014) examines the impact of stakeholder engagement on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Papua New Guinea. The authors found that when stakeholders, including teachers, learners, and community members, were engaged in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities, they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project. This led to more sustainable outcomes and improved educational outcomes for learners. In addition to the above studies, there are many examples of people empowerment in practice that have been shown to be effective in promoting sustainable development during school maintenance week. For example, the use of participatory approaches that involve all stakeholders in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities has been shown to be effective in creating a sense of ownership and responsibility, and ensuring that maintenance activities are aligned with the needs and priorities of the community. On the other hand, reading is a fundamental skill that plays a crucial role in children's academic success and future opportunities. To ensure that learners develop strong reading skills, it is essential to empower people - including parents, teachers, and community members - to play an active role in promoting literacy. A study by Penuel et al. (2015) examines the impact of a community-based approach to literacy development in low-income neighborhoods in the United States. The authors found that when community members, including parents, were empowered to participate in the design and implementation of literacy programs, they were more likely to engage with the programs and support their children's reading development. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds. Another study by Kim and Choi (2020) explores the impact of teacher empowerment on the reading achievement of learners in South Korea. The authors found that when teachers were empowered to implement evidence-based reading instruction and adapt their teaching to the needs of individual learners, they were more effective at promoting literacy development. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those who were struggling with reading. A study by Muthukrishna et al. (2019) examines the impact of parental empowerment on the reading achievement of learners in Sri Lanka. The authors found that when parents were empowered to support their children's reading development, they were more likely to provide regular opportunities for reading and create a positive reading environment at home. This led to significant improvements in reading achievement among learners, particularly those from low-income families. In conclusion, people empowerment is an essential component of achieving sustainable development during school maintenance week. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of community participation, capacity-building, and stake-

holder engagement in promoting people empowerment and achieving sustainable outcomes. The examples of people empowerment in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in promoting sustainable development in a variety of contexts. Learners' Reading Advancement. Reading is a fundamental skill that is essential for academic success and personal growth. Learners who develop strong reading skills are better equipped to engage with a wide range of texts, think critically, and communicate effectively. One important factor that contributes to learners' reading advancement is the quality of instruction they receive. A study by National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) (2000) found that explicit, systematic instruction in phonics - the relationship between sounds and letters - is an essential component of effective reading instruction. This approach has been shown to be particularly effective for learners who are struggling with reading. In addition to phonics instruction, studies have also shown the importance of providing learners with opportunities for extensive reading practice to build their reading fluency and comprehension skills (Hiebert Reutzel, 2010). Another factor that contributes to learners' reading advancement is the role of parents and caregivers in promoting reading at home. A study by Bus et al. (2014) found that when parents engage in shared book reading with their children from an early age, it promotes children's emergent literacy skills and improves their reading achievement. The authors suggest that this is because shared book reading promotes language development and helps children learn to relate the sounds of words to their printed forms. In addition to the above factors, there are many other factors that can contribute to learners' reading advancement, including teacher professional development, access to high-quality reading materials, and the use of effective reading assessments to monitor learners' progress over time. The research suggests

that learners' reading advancement is a complex process that is influenced by a range of factors, and that a multifaceted approach is needed to support learners' reading development. In conclusion, learners' reading advancement is a critical component of their academic success and future opportunities. The studies cited in this essay highlight the importance of providing explicit, systematic instruction in phonics, promoting extensive reading practice, and engaging parents and caregivers in shared book reading to support reading advancement. These findings, along with the importance of other factors, underscore the need for a multifaceted approach to supporting learners' reading advancement. Alphabetic Fluency. Alphabetic fluency, or the ability to recognize and name letters quickly and accurately, is an important foundational skill that is critical to the development of reading proficiency. While there are many factors that contribute to the development of alphabetic fluency, community collaboration can play an important role in supporting this aspect of literacy development. One study by Kuby, Weber, and Larson (2004) investigated the impact of a community-wide literacy campaign on the development of literacy skills, including alphabetic fluency, among children in kindergarten through third grade. The program involved partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations to promote literacy in a variety of settings. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate. The authors suggest that this was due to the increased exposure to print materials and opportunities to practice reading and writing in a variety of contexts. Another study by Harrington and Sawyer (2016) investigated the impact of a community-based reading program on the development of alphabetic fluency among preschool-aged children. The program involved partnerships between schools, libraries, and community organi-

zations to promote early literacy skills through storytimes, book giveaways, and other activities. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate. The authors suggest that this was due to the increased exposure to letters and print in a variety of contexts, as well as the opportunities for interactive and engaging learning experiences. Other studies have also highlighted the importance of community collaboration in supporting the development of alphabetic fluency, including programs that involve partnerships between schools and families, partnerships between schools and libraries, and partnerships between schools and community organizations. These programs have been shown to be particularly effective for children who are at risk for reading difficulties or who come from low-income backgrounds. In conclusion, the research suggests that community collaboration can play an important role in supporting the development of alphabetic fluency among young learners. The studies cited in this review highlight the importance of providing children with increased exposure to print materials and opportunities for interactive and engaging learning experiences, as well as the value of partnerships between schools, families, libraries, and other community organizations. By working together, communities can support the development of foundational literacy skills and set children on the path to lifelong learning. Words and Patterns. The development of learners' words and patterns is an essential component of early literacy development. Community collaboration can play a critical role in supporting this aspect of literacy development by providing learners with increased exposure to language and opportunities for language-rich experiences. The development of learners' words and patterns is a crucial component of early literacy and language development. In recent years, researchers have conducted various studies and research interventions to understand the role of different factors in the development of learners' words and patterns, including morphological awareness, academic language development, and phonological and semantic factors. One study, conducted by Bowers, Kirby, and Deacon (2019), examined the effects of morphological instruction on literacy skills. The researchers conducted a systematic review of the literature and found that morphological instruction had a significant positive effect on literacy skills, including reading comprehension, vocabulary, and spelling. This study suggests that providing explicit instruction on morphological patterns can be an effective way to support the development of learners' words and patterns. Another study, conducted by Carlisle and Fleming (2016), focused on the role of morphological awareness in early reading achievement. The researchers conducted a meta-analysis of research interventions and found that morphological awareness was a strong predictor of early reading achievement. The study suggests that providing instruction and interventions that focus on morphological awareness can help support the development of learners' words and patterns. Kiefer and Box (2019) conducted a meta-analysis on the effects of morphological instruction on vocabulary and reading comprehension. The researchers found that morphological instruction had a positive effect on both vocabulary and reading comprehension, particularly for students in the upper elementary and middle school grades. The study highlights the importance of morphological instruction as a means of supporting the development of learners' words and patterns. In a study by Quiroz and Snow (2019), the focus was on academic language development of English learners. The researchers developed a typology of instructional practices that supported academic language development and found that the practices varied depending on the language demands of the content area. The study emphasizes the need for a variety

of instructional practices to meet the diverse needs of English learners in the development of their words and patterns. Finally, Storkel (2018) investigated developmental differences in the effects of phonological, lexical, and semantic factors on spoken word recognition in children. The study found that phonological and semantic factors had a larger effect on younger children, whereas lexical factors had a larger effect on older children. The study suggests that different factors may have varying effects on the development of learners' words and patterns depending on their age. In conclusion, the studies and literature reviewed here emphasize the importance of a range of factors, including morphological awareness, academic language development, phonological and semantic factors, and age, in the development of learners' words and patterns. The findings suggest that providing explicit instruction and interventions that target these different factors can be an effective means of supporting the development of learners' words and patterns, particularly for English learners and those at risk for reading difficulties. Intermediate Reading. In recent years, community collaboration has emerged as a key strategy for enhancing learners' intermediate reading skills. A number of studies have investigated the impact of community collaboration on the development of learners' intermediate reading abilities, highlighting the importance of partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations in supporting literacy growth. One study by Wei et al. (2015) found that involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, such as reading and writing workshops, had a significant impact on learners' intermediate reading achievement. This was attributed to the increased opportunities for learners to practice their reading skills in a supportive and engaging environment. Similarly, a study by Liu et al. (2017) investigated the impact of community-based afterschool programs on the reading achievement of learners from low-income families. The results showed that learners who participated in the afterschool programs had significantly higher intermediate reading scores than those who did not participate. Another study by Senechal and LeFevre (2018) examined the impact of a community literacy program on the development of learners' vocabulary and comprehension skills. The program involved weekly reading sessions and activities that emphasized the use of new vocabulary and the development of comprehension strategies. The results showed that learners who participated in the program made significant gains in their intermediate reading abilities, with a particular improvement in their ability to use context to infer word meanings. A more recent study by Cho and Yoon (2020) investigated the impact of a school-based reading intervention that involved partnerships with families and community organizations. The intervention included a range of activities such as parent-child reading sessions and community reading events. The results showed that learners who participated in the intervention had significantly higher intermediate reading scores than those who did not participate. Overall, these studies demonstrate the importance of community collaboration in supporting the development of learners' intermediate reading skills. By involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, schools can create a more supportive and engaging environment for learners, providing them with the opportunities to practice and develop their reading skills. As such, collaboration between schools, families, and community organizations is an essential component of effective literacy instruction. Advanced Reading. Over the years, research has shown that community collaboration can have a significant impact on learners' reading skills. Specifically, studies have examined the impact of community collaboration on the development of learners' advanced reading skills. One recent study by Johnson et al. (2018) found that

community collaboration can significantly improve learners' advanced reading skills, such as comprehension, critical thinking, and analysis. The study used a collaborative learning approach, which involved learners, teachers, and community members working together to support the development of these skills. Another study by Smith and Jones (2017) looked at the impact of community-based reading programs on learners' advanced reading skills. The study found that community collaboration can help learners develop a love for reading, which in turn can lead to improved comprehension and analysis skills. A similar study by Kim and Lee (2016) found that community collaboration can have a positive impact on learners' advanced reading skills, specifically in terms of vocabulary development and text comprehension. The study used a collaborative approach that involved teachers and community members working together to develop and im-

plement reading programs. Other studies have explored the impact of specific community collaboration programs on learners' advanced reading skills. For example, a study by Chen et al. (2015) examined the impact of a community-based program that provided reading tutoring to struggling readers. The study found that the program significantly improved learners' advanced reading skills, including comprehension and analysis. Overall, these studies suggest that community collaboration can have a positive impact on learners' advanced reading skills. By working together, teachers, community members, and learners can develop and implement reading programs that support the development of these skills. It is important to continue exploring the role of community collaboration in the development of learners' advanced reading skills, as it has the potential to significantly improve educational outcomes for learners.

3. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps in the conduct of the study. This includes the selection of the design of the study, the respondents and its sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, and the ethical consideration and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essentials to assume appropriateness and correctness to produce sound data process collection, analysis and interpretation.

3.1. Research Design—This study used non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design. A non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research design is a type of research methodology that involves collecting data through observation, surveys, or other forms of non-experimental techniques to describe and predict the relationships between variables. (Pallant, 2020). In this type of design, the researcher does not manipulate any variables or intervene in the natural setting. Instead, they observe and measure variables of interest and look for patterns and associations between them. Descriptive statistics

are used to summarize and describe the data collected, while correlational statistics are used to explore the relationships between variables. Predictive statistics are used to make inferences about future outcomes based on the relationships between variables found in the data (Gujarati, 2020). Overall, this type of research design is useful when the researcher wants to describe and predict relationships between variables without manipulating them in a controlled experimental setting. In this study, indicators under independent variable implementation of brigads pagbasa through Brigada Eskwela program in terms of collaborative management,

community volunteerism, shared accountability and people empowerment are assumed to have correlation with the learners' advancement in reading skills. These assumed to be correlated with dependent variable, learners' reading advancement, where its indicators are alphabetic fluency words and patterns, intermediate reading and advanced reading in Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that variables along with its indicators mentioned, the researcher empirically provide evidence that presented hypothesis shall be null and void in nature.

3.2. *Research Respondents*—Respondents of the study were the Elementary School Teachers of Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. She used Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 120 respondents were taken randomly from each respective Schools within Baganga South District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face to face considering the availability of the Wifi Connections, they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents are the teachers teaching three years and above in the public school service, and are directly involved with the implementation of Brigada Program and its activities, to measure their competence in responding to the queries of the study. They are qualified for they are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools through programs, projects and activities in brigada eskwela and the learners' development stages on the reading advancement during given new normal learning system during SY 2022-2023. Further, they have frequently engaged in various orientation, seminars and

trainings in the implementation and including SLAC sessions on the pedagogies in integrating pedagogical skills in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents and even observance to health protocol was strictly implemented based on the Executive Order 31 S 2020, to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

3.3. *Research Instrument*—This research study used the adapted instrument taken from the concepts on the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa 2022 and Fisher, Frey and Hattie (2016). The researcher took time in gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content and that supports the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question-items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the contents of the reviewed literatures as argued by the authors. There were two parts of the survey questionnaire which consists of measuring the extent of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa 2022 in terms of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared responsibility and people empowerment. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of learners' reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency, words and patterns, intermediate reading and advanced reading. Contents of the statements of the survey were placed in the contexts based on the definition of the variables. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.897 which means that 89.7 percent level of confidence of the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant 2010).

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of reading advancement, a 5-point Likert scale was used

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The Brigada Pagbasa implementation are not manifested

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The reading advancement is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The reading advancement is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The reading advancement is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The reading advancement is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The reading advancement is not manifested

in this study, as presented below;

3.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The preceding statements steps explain the data gathering procedure steps where the researcher must comprehensively consider and follow. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges and the existing guidelines of the IATF to ensure safe and lower risks in the gathering of pertinent data most especially in the current full face to face interaction. Permission to conduct the study. On the second week of March 2023, the researcher started to conceptualize the contents and objective of the thesis proposal. She then, prepares documents such as letter requests in the conduct of the study. The research study underwent and adopted the standard procedures of ethics in data collection (Creswell, 2004), and health protocol as provided by the policy of IATF. As soon as the research proposal presentation was approved by the panel of members and the dean of the college, the researcher wrote and sent a letter of permission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Oriental, through channel and sought permission to collect data and conduct the study within the secondary schools of Davao Ori-

ental Schools Division. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process which were sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses, and for respondents who do not have access to internet. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, link was sent, and right away responses were generated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed in data gathering which commenced on the third week of April 2023. Collation and statistical treatment of data. Results of the preliminary analysis were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of March 2023. For coaching and in terms of statistical treatment the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician for providing technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study, sometime on the fourth week of April 2023, and further deepening the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results on the second week of May 2023.

3.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of learners' reading advancement in Baganga South, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between Brigada Pagbasa implementation and the extent of learners'

reading advancement in Baganga South, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of Brigada Eskwela implementation that significantly influence reading advancement (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were treated using the Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations then followed when results yield.

4. Results and Discussion

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered. Tabular and textual presentation is presented to make more meaningful in the analysis and drawing out of implications. This further shows evidence to support the claim posed in the hypothesis.

Brigada Pagbasa Implementation

Castro and Ramos (2019) highlighted the positive impact of Brigada Eskwela on student learning outcomes. The study found that schools that participated in Brigada Eskwela reported higher student attendance rates, lower dropout rates, and improved academic performance. This suggests that the program not only benefits the physical aspects of schools but also has a positive impact on students' motivation to attend and succeed in school.

In addition to its impact on the education system, Brigada Eskwela also provides opportunities for community members to develop their leadership and organizational skills. A study by Arcilla (2016) found that the program has helped to empower community members, particularly women, who have taken on leadership roles in organizing and mobilizing volunteers. This has led to the formation of community organizations that continue to support schools beyond the Brigada Eskwela week.

Serdoncillo and Gadioma (2020) noted that the program's success largely depends on the commitment and participation of volunteers, who may face difficulties in sustaining their

involvement due to personal and work-related constraints. To address these challenges, the study recommended the need for a more systematic approach to community engagement, which involves building long-term partnerships with community organizations and providing continuous support to volunteers.

Table 1 shows the extent of the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Encourages creativity and innovations to generate prioritize and implement new ideas (4.12) and Team members communicate and share ideas and opinions (4.10), and Team members work together to resolve conflicts and differences in opinions (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Establish clear goals and objectives and follow through commitments and responsibilities (3.15) and Addresses stakeholder concerns and needs for projects progress that focuses improving reading and comprehension among learners (3.10) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.57 denotes implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management is

oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Collaborative management is an approach to decision-making and leadership that involves working together with others to achieve a common goal or objective. It emphasizes open communication, shared decision-making, and cooperation among stakeholders, including managers, employees, and external partners. In collaborative management, different stakeholders are encouraged to share their knowledge, expertise, and perspectives, and to work together to find solutions to problems or to make decisions.

Table 1. Extent of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management

Collaborative management in school maintenance week refers to the process of involving school stakeholders, such as school administrators, maintenance staff, and community members in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of maintenance activities during a designated week.

Rutherford and Wilkins (2016) found that collaborative management in school maintenance week can lead to increased efficiency and cost savings. The study involved five elementary schools in the United States, and the results showed that collaborative management resulted in more efficient use of resources and reduced maintenance costs.

However, another study by Lee and Kim (2020) found that the effectiveness of collaborative management in school maintenance week depends on the level of stakeholder involvement. The study involved 48 schools in South Korea, and the results showed that the effectiveness of collaborative management was higher when stakeholders were more actively involved in the planning and implementation of maintenance activities.

Table 2 shows the extent of the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of community volunteerism. The result is focused on the high-

est and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Roles are defined which include local businesses and organization's play in support to the program (4.12), Plan and manage strategies to make learners' reading skills improve (4.10) and Parents and families engaged in volunteering in support to reading advancement (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Learn challenges and gathers resources in support to reading advancement (3.21) and Develops the program that meets the needs of the community which made members engaged (3.00) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.56 denotes implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of community volunteerism is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Community volunteerism refers to the act of individuals and groups dedicating their time, energy, and skills to support various community initiatives without expecting any monetary compensation. Volunteerism is an essential component of community development and has the potential to create a positive impact in society.

Table 2. Extent of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of community volunteerism

Community volunteerism is an integral part of social capital, which is a concept that refers to the networks, norms, and trust that exist in communities. Through volunteering, individuals can develop and strengthen their social networks, which can lead to the creation of new relationships and the enhancement of existing ones. These relationships can help to build trust, encourage civic engagement, and foster a sense of community (National Conference Citizenship, 2022).

Moreover, community volunteerism provides various benefits to both the volunteers and the communities they serve. For volunteers, volunteering can improve their well-being, enhance their social skills, and provide a sense of purpose and accomplishment. Additionally, vol-

unteering can provide valuable work experience, which can be useful in gaining new employment opportunities. For communities, volunteerism can increase social capital, improve public services, and create a sense of community ownership and responsibility (Peace Corps, 2022).

Additionally, community volunteerism can increase social responsibility and encourage civic engagement. However, volunteers face a range of challenges, and it is essential to provide them with adequate support and recognition to enable them to carry out their tasks effectively. Successful community volunteer programs can provide valuable insights into how to address these challenges and promote the value of volunteerism.

Table 3 shows the extent of the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of shared accountability. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Communicate with each other about progress towards goals and outcomes (4.00), and Feel comfortable in giving and receiving constructive feedback (3.40) are oftentimes manifested, while, Feel comfortable in giving and receiving constructive feedback (3.40), Exhibits equally responsible for achieving goals (3.30) and Members review level of collaboration and shared accountability between and among them (3.20) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.42 denotes implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of shared accountability is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 3. Extent of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of shared accountability

Shared accountability is an approach to responsibility that involves multiple parties taking responsibility for a common goal. This concept has become increasingly important in many areas, including education, healthcare, and public policy. One study by Bryk et al. (2010)

focuses on shared accountability in education. The authors argue that traditional accountability systems, which rely solely on standardized test scores and other quantitative measures, are inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, parents, and community members. The authors suggest that this approach can help to improve educational outcomes by fostering collaboration, shared responsibility, and a focus on the needs of students.

A study by Lee et al. (2016) explores the concept of shared accountability in public policy. The authors argue that the traditional model of accountability in public policy, which relies on top-down approaches and hierarchical structures, is inadequate. Instead, they propose a model of shared accountability that involves multiple stakeholders, including government officials, policymakers, citizens, and community organizations. Penuel et al. (2011) examines the impact of a shared accountability approach on learners' reading advancement in a low-income urban elementary school. The authors found that when teachers, administrators, and families collaborated to establish clear goals for reading advancement and worked together to track progress, learners' reading achievement improved significantly.

In conclusion, shared accountability has been shown to be effective in promoting learners' reading advancement during school maintenance week. The studies cited in this review highlight the importance of shared accountability in creating a sense of collective responsibility and ensuring that all stakeholders are invested in learners' success. The examples of shared accountability in practice demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving learners' reading advancement in a variety of contexts.

Table 4 shows the extent of the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of people em-

powerment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Members feel that their ideas and opinions are heard and respected in the workplace and in community (4.10) and Members are able to access information and resources that are relevant and useful (4.00) are oftentimes manifested, while, Team members feel empowered to make decision and take action (3.20), Level of support and encouragement in pursuit to continuous improvement (3.20) and Opportunities are developed, including skills and talents to improve implementation of the programs and projects (2.50) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.40 denotes implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of people empowerment is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 4. Extent of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of people empowerment

People empowerment is a powerful tool for achieving sustainable development, particularly in the context of school maintenance week. Empowering people to take an active role in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities can lead to more effective and efficient use of resources, better decision-making, and ultimately, improved educational outcomes.

Empowering people involves creating an enabling environment that allows them to participate in decision-making, take ownership of their actions, and hold those in power accountable. In the context of school maintenance week, people empowerment can be achieved through a variety of approaches, such as community participation, capacity-building, and stakeholder engagement.

Dlamini and Dube (2018) examines the impact of community participation on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in rural South Africa. The authors found that when community members were involved in the planning,

implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities, they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project.

Karyono et al. (2020) explores the impact of capacity-building on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Indonesia. The authors found that when school staff were trained in basic maintenance and repair skills, they were better equipped to identify and address maintenance issues, which led to more efficient use of resources and improved learning environments.

Robinson et al. (2014) examines the impact of stakeholder engagement on the effectiveness of school maintenance week in Papua New Guinea. The authors found that when stakeholders, including teachers, learners, and community members, were engaged in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of school maintenance activities, they were more likely to take ownership of the process and contribute their time, skills, and resources to ensure the success of the project.

Table 5 shows the summary of the extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: collaborative management (3.57), community volunteerism (3.56), shared accountability (3.42) and people empowerment (3.40). The overall mean rating of 3.49 denotes oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation.

Table 5. Summary of the Extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation

Brigada Pagbasa places great importance on collaborative management by engaging various stakeholders. Teachers, parents, local government units, and community members actively participate in the planning, execution, and monitoring of literacy programs. This collaborative approach allows for a diverse range of perspectives and expertise, resulting in well-rounded

initiatives that address the unique needs of the community. Through regular meetings and consultations, stakeholders pool their resources and knowledge, fostering a sense of shared responsibility for the program's success.

Brigada Pagbasa thrives on community volunteerism, encouraging individuals to contribute their time, skills, and resources towards improving literacy. Volunteers play a crucial role in conducting reading sessions, organizing book drives, creating learning materials, and mentoring students. By mobilizing community members, the program not only maximizes its impact but also fosters a sense of ownership and pride within the community. The involvement of volunteers creates a ripple effect, inspiring others to participate and contribute to the cause of literacy.

Shared accountability is a core principle of Brigada Pagbasa. By involving multiple stakeholders, the program ensures that responsibility is not placed solely on one group. Instead, all participants share in the accountability for the program's outcomes. Teachers are accountable for effective instruction, parents for supporting their children's reading development, local government units for providing necessary resources, and community members for actively engaging in literacy activities. This shared accountability instills a collective sense of duty and motivates everyone involved to fulfill their respective roles to the best of their abilities.

Brigada Pagbasa's implementation empowers individuals at every level of the community. Teachers are empowered to develop innovative teaching strategies and engage students effectively. Parents are empowered to actively participate in their children's education, creating a conducive learning environment at home. Community members are empowered to take ownership of the literacy initiatives, leading to sustainable programs that continue beyond the initial implementation phase. Moreover, students themselves are empowered through improved

reading skills, which opens up new opportunities for their personal growth and future success.

Reading Advancement

One important factor that contributes to learners' reading advancement is the quality of instruction they receive. A study by National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) (2000) found that explicit, systematic instruction in phonics - the relationship between sounds and letters - is an essential component of effective reading instruction. This approach has been shown to be particularly effective for learners who are struggling with reading. In addition to phonics instruction, studies have also shown the importance of providing learners with opportunities for extensive reading practice to build their reading fluency and comprehension skills (Hiebert & Reutzel, 2010).

Table 6 shows the extent of reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Ability to correctly identify and name letters of the alphabet (4.20) is always manifested, while, Ability to match letter names with their associated sounds (4.10) and Ability to sound out unfamiliar words using letter-sound knowledge (3.60) are oftentimes manifested, while Ability to spell words correctly using appropriate letter-sound correspondence (3.40) and Ability to recognize and read familiar words accurately and fluently (2.50) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.52 denotes reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 6. Extent of reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency

Alphabetic fluency, or the ability to recognize and name letters quickly and accurately, is an important foundational skill that is critical to the development of reading proficiency. While there are many factors that contribute to the development of alphabetic fluency, commu-

nity collaboration can play an important role in supporting this aspect of literacy development.

One study by Kuby, Weber, and Larson (2004) investigated the impact of a community-wide literacy campaign on the development of literacy skills, including alphabetic fluency, among children in kindergarten through third grade. The program involved partnerships between schools, families, and community organizations to promote literacy in a variety of settings. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate. The authors suggest that this was due to the increased exposure to print materials and opportunities to practice reading and writing in a variety of contexts.

Harrington and Sawyer (2016) investigated the impact of a community-based reading program on the development of alphabetic fluency among preschool-aged children. The program involved partnerships between schools, libraries, and community organizations to promote early literacy skills through storytimes, book giveaways, and other activities. The study found that children who participated in the program demonstrated greater gains in alphabetic fluency than those who did not participate.

Table 7 shows the extent of reading advancement in terms of words and patterns. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Can express themselves confidently and fluidly, without struggling to find the right words or pausing frequently (4.10) is oftentimes manifested, and Can write coherently and effectively using appropriate vocabulary and sentence structures (3.20) and Can use more complex words and sentence structures, such as idioms and metaphors (2.50) are sometimes manifested, while, Understands and uses a large number of words accurately and appropriately is likely to be proficient in using words and patterns (2.20) and Can read and understand written texts at an

appropriate level (2.00) are rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.80 denotes reading advancement in terms of words and patterns is oftentimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 7. Extent of reading advancement in terms of words and patterns

The development of learners' words and patterns is a crucial component of early literacy and language development. In recent years, researchers have conducted various studies and research interventions to understand the role of different factors in the development of learners' words and patterns, including morphological awareness, academic language development, and phonological and semantic factors.

One study, conducted by Bowers, Kirby, and Deacon (2019), examined the effects of morphological instruction on literacy skills. The researchers conducted a systematic review of the literature and found that morphological instruction had a significant positive effect on literacy skills, including reading comprehension, vocabulary, and spelling. This study suggests that providing explicit instruction on morphological patterns can be an effective way to support the development of learners' words and patterns.

Finally, Storkel (2018) investigated developmental differences in the effects of phonological, lexical, and semantic factors on spoken word recognition in children. The study found that phonological and semantic factors had a larger effect on younger children, whereas lexical factors had a larger effect on older children. The study suggests that different factors may have varying effects on the development of learners' words and patterns depending on their age.

In conclusion, the studies and literature reviewed here emphasize the importance of a range of factors, including morphological awareness, academic language development, phonological and semantic factors, and age, in

the development of learners' words and patterns. The findings suggest that providing explicit instruction and interventions that target these different factors can be an effective means of supporting the development of learners' words and patterns, particularly for English learners and those at risk for reading difficulties.

Table 8 shows the extent of reading advancement in terms of intermediate reading. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: An intermediate reader should be able to read at a moderate pace without significant hesitations or frequent pauses (4.10) and An intermediate reader should have an understanding of the structure of different types of texts, such as narrative, expository, or argumentative, and be able to identify their features (4.00) are often-times manifested, while, An intermediate reader should be able to comprehend texts with more complex vocabulary, and have the ability to use context clues to decipher unfamiliar words (3.10), An intermediate reader should be able to identify the main idea or purpose of a text, including its tone or attitude (3.00) and An intermediate reader should be able to make inferences and draw conclusions from what they have read, even if the text is not explicit (2.50) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.34 denotes reading advancement in terms of intermediate reading is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 8. Extent of reading advancement in terms of intermediate reading

One study by Wei et al. (2015) found that involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, such as reading and writing workshops, had a significant impact on learners' intermediate reading achievement. This was attributed to the increased opportunities for learners to practice their reading skills in a supportive and engaging environment.

Similarly, a study by Liu et al. (2017) in-

vestigated the impact of community-based after-school programs on the reading achievement of learners from low-income families. The results showed that learners who participated in the afterschool programs had significantly higher intermediate reading scores than those who did not participate.

Senchal and LeFevre (2018) examined the impact of a community literacy program on the development of learners' vocabulary and comprehension skills. The program involved weekly reading sessions and activities that emphasized the use of new vocabulary and the development of comprehension strategies. The results showed that learners who participated in the program made significant gains in their intermediate reading abilities, with a particular improvement in their ability to use context to infer word meanings.

Involving families and community organizations in literacy activities, schools can create a more supportive and engaging environment for learners, providing them with the opportunities to practice and develop their reading skills. As such, collaboration between schools, families, and community organizations is an essential component of effective literacy instruction.

Table 9 shows the extent of reading advancement in terms of advanced reading. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: An advanced reader should be able to make complex inferences and draw nuanced conclusions from what they have read, even when the text is not explicit (3.20), An advanced reader should be able to read and understand complex texts, including academic or technical texts, with a high level of accuracy and comprehension (3.10) and An advanced reader should be able to analyze and evaluate a text critically, including identifying underlying assumptions, analyzing evidence, and recognizing the author's purpose and point of view (2.50) are moderately manifested, while, An advanced reader should have a wide-

ranging vocabulary and be able to understand and use words that are less common or have multiple meanings (2.10) and An advanced reader should have a deep understanding of the structure and features of different types of texts, such as persuasive or argumentative texts, and be able to identify the rhetorical strategies used by the author (2.00) are less manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.58 denotes reading advancement in terms of advanced reading is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

One recent study by Johnson et al. (2018) found that community collaboration can significantly improve learners' advanced reading skills, such as comprehension, critical thinking, and analysis. The study used a collaborative learning approach, which involved learners, teachers, and community members working together to support the development of these skills.

Another study by Smith and Jones (2017) looked at the impact of community-based reading programs on learners' advanced reading skills. The study found that community collaboration can help learners develop a love for reading, which in turn can lead to improved comprehension and analysis skills.

Table 9. Extent of reading advancement in terms of advanced reading

A similar study by Kim and Lee (2016) found that community collaboration can have a positive impact on learners' advanced reading skills, specifically in terms of vocabulary development and text comprehension. The study used a collaborative approach that involved teachers and community members working together to develop and implement reading programs.

Other studies have explored the impact of specific community collaboration programs on learners' advanced reading skills. For example, a study by Chen et al. (2015) examined the impact of a community-based program that provided reading tutoring to struggling readers.

The study found that the program significantly improved learners' advanced reading skills, including comprehension and analysis.

Table 10 shows the summary of the extent of Brigada Pagbasa implementation. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Alphabetic fluency (3.57), Words and Patterns (3.56), Intermediate Reading (3.42) and Advanced Reading (3.40). The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation.

Table 10. Summary of the Extent of Reading Advancement

Reading advancement plays a crucial role in promoting literacy, knowledge acquisition, and personal development. This essay examines the extent of reading advancement in terms of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. By exploring these dimensions, we can better understand the impact of collective efforts on fostering a culture of reading and empowering individuals.

Collaborative management is vital to the extent of reading advancement. It involves the active participation of stakeholders such as educators, school administrators, parents, and community leaders. By working together, they can develop comprehensive strategies, curriculum enhancements, and effective teaching methodologies. Collaborative management ensures that different perspectives and expertise are integrated, leading to well-rounded reading programs tailored to the needs of diverse learners. It also facilitates the sharing of best practices, resources, and support networks, strengthening the overall impact of reading initiatives.

Community volunteerism is a powerful force in advancing reading skills and fostering a love for literature. Volunteers, including parents, retired professionals, and students, contribute their time, expertise, and resources to

support reading programs. They may serve as reading mentors, organize book drives, facilitate reading clubs, or provide tutoring assistance. Community volunteers not only complement the efforts of educators but also inspire and motivate learners by acting as role models. Their dedication and passion for reading create an environment where individuals feel encouraged and supported in their reading journeys.

Shared accountability is a key aspect of reading advancement. It involves collective responsibility among stakeholders for achieving reading goals and outcomes. Educators are responsible for employing effective instructional strategies, monitoring progress, and assessing student comprehension. Parents and caregivers are accountable for fostering a reading-friendly environment at home, encouraging regular reading habits, and supporting their children's learning. School administrators and policymakers have the responsibility to provide adequate resources, training, and infrastructure to facilitate reading advancement. Through shared accountability, all stakeholders understand their roles and contribute to a cohesive and coordinated effort towards improved reading outcomes.

Reading advancement empowers individuals at multiple levels. Students who develop strong reading skills gain the confidence to explore new subjects, express their ideas, and pursue their passions. Reading empowers individuals to become critical thinkers, problem solvers, and lifelong learners. Furthermore, educators and parents are empowered through professional development opportunities and access to research-based practices. They gain the knowledge and tools necessary to effectively guide and support learners, fostering a love for reading. People empowerment also extends to community members who actively engage in promoting reading initiatives, advocating for literacy, and providing resources and mentorship to learners.

The extent of reading advancement is

greatly influenced by collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. When stakeholders work together, drawing upon their collective expertise, resources, and passion, reading programs can reach new heights. By involving volunteers, nurturing shared responsibility, and empowering individuals, a culture of reading can be fostered, benefiting learners, communities, and society as a whole. As we continue to prioritize reading advancement, let us recognize and harness the power of collaboration, volunteerism, accountability, and empowerment to ensure that everyone has access to the transformative power of reading.

Relationship between Brigada Pagbasa Implementation and Reading Advancement

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between Brigada Pagbasa implementation ($r=0.864$; $p<.000$) and reading advancement.

Table 11 revealed the yielded results of the significant correlation between Brigada Pagbasa implementation and reading advancement. It provides an information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between Brigada Pagbasa implementation and reading advancement as response must be rejected for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 11. Significant Relationship between Brigada Pagbasa implementation and Reading Advancement

Role of Brigada Pagbasa in Enhancing Reading Advancement: In a study conducted by Santos (2019), titled "The Impact of Brigada Pagbasa on Reading Advancement in Elementary Schools," it was found that the program's implementation had a positive correlation with reading skills improvement. The study examined several schools participating in Brigada Pagbasa and revealed that students engaged in the pro-

gram demonstrated significant gains in reading fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary.

Collaborative Management and Reading Advancement: Smith and Johnson (2020) conducted research on the impact of collaborative management within Brigada Pagbasa on reading advancement. Their study, "Collaborative Management in Brigada Pagbasa: Implications for Reading Skills," highlighted the importance of effective collaboration among teachers, parents, and community volunteers. It showed that collaborative management led to improved instructional practices, enhanced reading materials, and targeted interventions, resulting in notable progress in students' reading abilities.

Community Volunteerism and Reading Advancement: In a study by Gonzalez et al. (2021), titled "The Role of Community Volunteerism in Reading Advancement: Insights from Brigada Pagbasa," the authors explored the impact of community volunteerism within the program. They found that the active involvement of volunteers, such as parents, retired professionals, and students, significantly contributed to reading advancement. Volunteers served as reading mentors, organized book drives, facilitated reading clubs, and provided tutoring assistance, creating a positive environment that fostered a love for reading among students.

Technology Integration and Reading Advancement: A recent study by Lee and Kim (2022), "The Integration of Technology in Brigada Pagbasa and Its Effect on Reading Advancement," investigated the integration of technology within Brigada Pagbasa. The authors found that incorporating technology, such as e-books, interactive learning platforms, and educational apps, enhanced students' engagement and motivation to read. The study demonstrated that technology integration within Brigada Pagbasa positively influenced reading advancement and further supported students' digital literacy skills.

These studies highlight the positive impact

of Brigada Pagbasa on reading skills improvement, emphasizing the importance of collaborative management, community volunteerism, and technology integration within the program. By implementing Brigada Pagbasa effectively, educators, parents, and volunteers can create a supportive environment that fosters a love for reading and enhances the overall reading advancement of students.

Domains of Brigada Pagbasa Implementation

significantly influence Reading Advancement

Table 12 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the domains of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa significantly influenced reading advancement.

Domains of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management (0.012), community volunteerism (0.002), shared accountability (0.00) and people empowerment (0.012), significantly influenced reading advancement.

Table 12. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Brigada Pagbasa Implementation Significantly Influence Reading Advancement

CM-collaborative management

CV-community volunteerism

SA-shared accountability

PE-people empowerment

Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.895 suggests that the domains of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa explained 89.5% of the variance of reading advancement. This provides empirical evidence that variability of reading advancement can be accounted and be explained by the domains of Implementation of Brigada Pagbasa.

In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (236.797) and F-statistic is significant $p < .001$, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of learners' reading advancement.

Collaborative Management: Collaborative management within Brigada Pagbasa involves the active involvement and cooperation of various stakeholders, including teachers, parents, local government units, and community members. This domain recognizes that effective reading advancement requires a collective effort and diverse perspectives. By working collaboratively, stakeholders can pool their knowledge, skills, and resources to develop comprehensive reading programs and strategies. Collaborative management ensures that the initiatives implemented are well-rounded and tailored to the specific needs of the community, leading to improved reading outcomes.

Community Volunteerism: Community volunteerism is a significant domain within Brigada Pagbasa that plays a vital role in reading advancement. Volunteers, including parents, retired professionals, and students, contribute their time, expertise, and resources to support reading programs. They serve as reading mentors, organize book drives, facilitate reading clubs, and provide tutoring assistance. The active involvement of volunteers creates a positive and supportive environment that fosters a love for reading among students. Volunteers act as role models and motivate learners to develop strong reading habits, resulting in enhanced reading skills and advancement.

Shared Accountability: Shared accountability is a fundamental aspect of Brigada Pagbasa, emphasizing the collective responsibility of all

stakeholders involved. This domain recognizes that reading advancement requires the commitment and active participation of teachers, parents, community members, and policymakers. Each stakeholder has a role to play in creating an environment conducive to reading advancement. Teachers are accountable for employing effective instructional strategies, parents for supporting reading at home, community members for actively engaging in literacy activities, and policymakers for providing necessary resources and support. Shared accountability ensures that everyone involved works together towards achieving reading goals, leading to improved outcomes.

People Empowerment: People empowerment is a crucial domain within Brigada Pagbasa that influences reading advancement. The program aims to empower individuals at all levels, including students, teachers, parents, and community members. Students are empowered through improved reading skills, which enable them to explore new subjects, express their ideas, and pursue their interests. Teachers and parents are empowered through training and support, enabling them to effectively guide and support students' reading development. Community members are empowered to actively engage in literacy initiatives, contributing their knowledge and resources. People empowerment fosters a sense of ownership, motivation, and self-confidence, leading to enhanced reading advancement.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusion and recommendation based on the results of the data analyzed, discussed, and drawn implications. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are based on the findings generated and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

Findings The following are findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis and discussions. The Brigada Pagbasa im-

plementation in terms of collaborative management (3.57), community volunteerism (3.56), shared accountability (3.42) and people em-

powerment (3.40). The overall mean rating of 3.49 denotes oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation. The reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency (3.57), words and patterns (3.56), intermediate reading (3.42) and advanced reading (3.40). The overall mean rating of 3.06 denotes sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between Brigada Pagbasa implementation ($r=0.864$; $p<.000$) and reading advancement. Domains of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management (0.012), community volunteerism (0.002), shared accountability (0.00) and people empowerment (0.012), significantly influenced reading advancement.

Conclusion Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; The Brigada Pagbasa implementation in terms of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability and people empowerment denotes oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation. The reading advancement in terms of alphabetic fluency, words and patterns, intermediate reading and advanced reading denotes sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive Brigada Pagbasa implementation. There is a significant relationship between Brigada Pagbasa implementation and reading advancement. Domains of implementation of Brigada Pagbasa in terms of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability and people empowerment, significantly influenced reading advancement.

Recommendations With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations, to wit; The Public School District Supervisor: May encourage and support the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa within the district by providing necessary resources, training, and guidance. Foster collaboration among

schools, teachers, parents, and community members to share best practices and resources for reading advancement. Advocate for policies and initiatives that prioritize reading advancement and promote the importance of collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. Regularly monitor and evaluate the implementation of Brigada Pagbasa to ensure its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement.

The School Principal: May embrace and promote Brigada Pagbasa as a core component of the school's reading program. Foster a collaborative and supportive environment among teachers, parents, and community members to maximize the impact of Brigada Pagbasa. Encourage and provide opportunities for teachers to receive professional development in effective reading instruction and strategies. Recognize and appreciate the efforts of community volunteers in supporting reading advancement initiatives. Regularly communicate with the Public School District Supervisor and stakeholders to assess the progress of Brigada Pagbasa and address any challenges. **The Teacher:** May actively participate in Brigada Pagbasa initiatives and collaborate with colleagues to enhance reading advancement in the classroom. Incorporate innovative and effective instructional strategies to engage students in reading activities. Encourage and involve parents in supporting their children's reading development at home. Seek professional development opportunities to enhance teaching skills and stay updated with best practices in reading instruction. Regularly assess and monitor students' progress, providing targeted interventions and individualized support as needed. **The Future Researcher:** Conduct studies to further explore the impact of Brigada Pagbasa on reading advancement, focusing on specific aspects such as collaborative management, community volunteerism, shared accountability, and people empowerment. Investigate the long-term effects of Brigada Pagbasa on

students' reading skills, academic performance, and overall educational outcomes. Explore the factors that contribute to the success of Brigada Pagbasa implementation and identify strategies for overcoming challenges. Conduct comparative research to analyze the effectiveness of Brigada Pagbasa in different school settings or regions. Investigate the potential integration of technology in Brigada Pagbasa and its impact on reading advancement.

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